

FOSTERING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: DEVELOPING TEACHERS' UNDERSTANDING AND COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *Recently higher education reforms in Uzbekistan have turned inclusive education into a core element reflecting the country's commitment to bringing about equal access to all learners while matching worldwide educational trends that build such environments where every student has a “room to grow”. This, diversification, whereby every student is a benefit, is a principle from which the educational experience springs, and simultaneously the barriers that members of some groups such as those from the countryside or minority linguistic communities, who may need customized support to be able to fully join academic content, are also recognized. The inclusivity focus, therefore, aligns Uzbekistan's national education policies with the overall educational strategy of building a more equal and resilient education system which enables the students to contribute to the socio-economic development of the country by breaking through social mobility barriers. More so, it also emphasizes the country's devotion to international standards and conventions among which the UNESCO guidelines that advocate for inclusive education systems that acknowledge diversity as an intrinsic human right and a driving force for social progress.*

Key words: *Inclusive education, Uzbekistan, higher education, teacher development, cultural competence, differentiated instruction, professional learning, Universal Design for Learning.*

One of the vital elements of promoting inclusive education within Uzbekistan's higher education system is creating an inclusive educational culture among university teachers and administrators. The success of this program requires the development of an all-new mindset, values, and pedagogical practices, which should be away from those methods that possibly exclude certain groups of students. However, current attempts emphasize responsive and adaptive learning environments that are used to engage all students and address every student's unique and diverse needs. The school's mission includes providing opportunities to children with various abilities that may not necessarily mean turning them into skilled performers and encompassing diversified teaching, assessment, and support mechanisms that are adjusted to individual learners. The promotion of cultural competence, a framework that accentuates teachers' capacity to comprehend, appreciate, and involve with the cultural, linguistic, and social diversity of their students, is the centerpiece of this paradigm shift (Banks & Banks, 2019; Gay, 2018). Through the integration of the aspect of cultural competence into teaching practices, educators are better positioned to wield the intersectionality of students' identities and thus provide higher education that is equitable, accessible, and empowering for all.

Ultimately, the development of an inclusive educational culture within Uzbekistan's higher education system represents a holistic endeavor requiring sustained commitment from faculty, administrators, and policymakers. By prioritizing professional development, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, and embedding principles of cultural competence into teaching practices, higher education institutions in Uzbekistan can align with global standards of

inclusivity and equity. This transformation not only enhances the educational experiences of all students but also contributes to broader societal goals of reducing inequality, promoting social cohesion, and building a more inclusive and equitable future.

The success of inclusive education in Uzbek universities depends on the development of teachers in universities. Such development should address ongoing training in integrated pedagogies, including Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and differentiated instruction, both of which are important for meeting the needs of diverse students. UDL supports the creation of a flexible learning environment that accommodates a variety of learning styles and interests, offering a variety of participation, teaching, and instructional styles (Meyer, Rose, & Gordon, 2014). Florian and Black-Hawkins (2011) state that teachers trained in UDL can create better curricula that support learning and assessment, creating a mixed environment where students of all abilities can thrive. Similarly, as Tomlinson (2014) points out, differentiated instruction allows teachers to adapt their instruction and materials to the individual needs of their students. Therefore, professional development programs should go beyond theoretical knowledge and focus on providing teachers with practical tools and strategies to create and sustain an environment around education (Ainscow, Booth, & Dyson, 2006; Florian & Linklater, 2010).

Collaboration between teachers across disciplines is another element in promoting collaboration in Uzbek universities. Interdisciplinary collaboration, particularly through the co-teaching of general education teachers and special education teachers, has shown its effectiveness in improving practice in different learning environments (Friend & Cook, 2016). Promoting this collaborative model in the Uzbek context can bridge the gap between theoretical concepts of inclusion and their practical application. These collaborations ensure that teachers not only understand the content that supports learning, but are also able to use it effectively in their classrooms (Forlin, 2010). In addition, Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) provide a platform for teachers to engage in peer mentoring, share new pedagogies, and reflect on their teaching. PLCs facilitate ongoing dialogue and professional exchange, helping teachers improve their instructional strategies and create a supportive and equitable environment for all students (DuFour & Fullan, 2013).

In the Uzbek context, several scholars have contributed significantly to the discussions on inclusive education, highlighting the challenges and opportunities that exist. Recent studies by Omonov (2019), Madrahimov (2020), Sharipov (2021), and Khusanov (2018) highlight the challenges that higher education institutions continue to face in implementing inclusive practices. These challenges include limited school resources, entrenched traditional educational practices, and a lack of training of university staff in inclusive education. Despite these obstacles, Fayzievna (2020) demonstrates the growing recognition that inclusive education is a key factor in ensuring equitable access to higher education and promoting educational success for all students, regardless of their background.

The main obstacle to promoting inclusive education in the higher education system of Uzbekistan is the need for teachers to respond to criticism and suspicions about students' abilities. This problem is particularly acute for students from disadvantaged groups such as rural students, minorities, and those with disabilities. Research consistently finds that teachers' lower expectations of students from disadvantaged backgrounds have a negative impact on students' performance, self-efficacy, and sense of belonging in an educational environment (Ferguson, 2003; Nieto, 2010). Eliminating these practices is an important part of fostering an inclusive educational culture. Teachers should engage in reflective practices that encourage self-evaluation of their beliefs and promote appropriate teaching practices (Schon, 1983). Such reflective

practices can help shape attitudes and foster an educational environment that values diversity and inclusion. Systemic challenges within the higher education framework in Uzbekistan make it increasingly difficult to implement inclusive education. Policies that focus on standardized tests and rigorous performance evaluations tend to reinforce a universal approach to education without considering the diverse needs of students, especially those from minority or marginalized groups (Waitoller and Artiles, 2013). These systemic barriers not only limit the scope of enrollment but also perpetuate disparities within the education system. To address these challenges, higher education institutions in Uzbekistan need to address diversity, equity, and inclusion as core principles of their curricula. This shift requires developing and implementing policies that support flexible and responsive teaching methods while fostering an institutional culture that values inclusion.

Professional development is a cornerstone of this transformation. Many faculty members in Uzbekistan’s higher education system have limited exposure to inclusive education practices due to a lack of targeted training programs. Professional development initiatives must not only introduce theoretical concepts but also provide practical, hands-on strategies that educators can apply in their classrooms. For instance, training sessions on differentiated instruction, as advocated by Tomlinson (2014), can help faculty design learning experiences that cater to students' individual needs. Furthermore, professional development should include modules on cultural competence, enabling educators to better understand and respect the diverse cultural and social identities of their students (Banks & Banks, 2019; Gay, 2018). Cultural competence training is particularly relevant in Uzbekistan, a nation characterized by its ethnic and linguistic diversity, as it helps educators create an inclusive environment where all students feel valued and understood.

Another critical area for fostering inclusivity is addressing faculty biases and assumptions about students’ capabilities. Implicit biases, often unrecognized by educators themselves, can significantly impact student outcomes, particularly for those from rural areas, minority groups, or with disabilities. Reflective practices, as proposed by Schon (1983), are an essential tool for combating these biases. Reflective practice encourages educators to critically evaluate their teaching methods, interactions with students, and underlying assumptions, fostering a more equity-driven approach to education. In this way, educators can actively challenge their biases and strive to create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment.

In summary, the development of inclusive education in Uzbekistan's higher education institutions is a multifaceted and ongoing process that requires commitment to professional development, reflection, and collaboration between teachers. While significant challenges remain, there are clear strategies that can be used to create an inclusive learning environment. By investing in the professional development of teachers, encouraging peer collaboration, and adopting inclusive teaching frameworks, Uzbekistan’s higher education system can continue to move toward providing equitable and inclusive education for all students. Research conducted by Uzbek scholars such as Omonov, Madalakhimov, Sharipov, and Kusanov, as well as international perspectives, provides valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities for inclusion in the country’s higher education system.

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